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University of Jember
May 13-14th, 2017

Dean of Faculty of Teacher Training and Education

Prof. Drs. Dafik, M.Sc., Ph.D

THE TRANSFORMATION OF OBJECT REPRESENTATIONS OF STUDENT'S VISUAL ON GEOMETRY PROBLEM SOLVING

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ABSTRACT

Geometry is one of many ways to understand the real world, since we can find Geometry concept in real life daily applications. Through some nets of a cube dices, the researcher would like to explore the transformation of object representation. How is the 5th grade elementary school student being able to transform an object representation? Actually it is a process which using the principles of transformation to describe an object with language, pictures or gestures. The subjects of this study were the concepts of students visual in 5th grade of elementary school. The researcher conducted a learning style test to the 5th grade students and gave a geometry problem to them; these can be used to indicate the profile the transformation of object representation on visual subject. The result of the research showed that subjects using a frame of reference, changing the point of view from 2 dimensions to 3 dimensions object, it was changing the shape of 2D to 3D by their imagination and also moving the objects.

Key Words: Transformation of Representations object; Visual; Geometry Problem Solving.

INTRODUCTION

Geometry is one of the brunch of science that plays a major role and the development of science and technology. The spatial object is one of the studies of geometry. Geometry develops due to the process of thinking. Therefore, special attention is needed to sharpen the ability of thinking that should be start from Elementary School so that it helps in improving their geometry knowledge that useful in the future for their knowledge and technology. Sharpening the ability of spatial thinking is one of aspect that can develop human creativity. The representation of the object is one of the spatial thinking factors on how to Change the shape of an object, change the viewing angle, change the frame of view, resize, move places, arrange parts, zoom in and out an object, and rotate the object. The importance of the transformation role of object representation in supporting the development of science and technology, it is necessary by the researcher, because there is a process of thinking how the process of transformation of object representation done by students when solving geometry problems. The subject chosen is a 5th grade student because according to Piaget's opinion that children build their knowledge in response to their experiences, children learn something in their own way without any interference from older children, and children are intrinsically motivated to Learning without any motivation to get an appreciation from others. The curiosity, intrinsic motivation without the basic reward that these children have become the basis for thinking in taking the subject and still in concrete operation phase

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The First International Conference of Natural and Social Science Education

It is with my great pleasure and honor to announce the "The First International Conference of Natural and Social Science Education 2017" which will be held from 13 -14 May 2017 in the University of Jember, East Java, Indonesia. It is the first international conference organised by Jember Literacy of Lesson Study, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, University of Jember in cooperation with Indonesian Association of Lesson Study. The conference is held to welcome participants from around the world, with broad and diverse research interests. The mission is to become an annual international forum in the future, where, civil society organization and representative, research students, academics and researchers, scholars, scientist, teachers and practitioners from all over the world could meet in and exchange an idea to share and to discuss theoretical and practical knowledge about an education issue in the ASEAN + 8 community era.

The aim of the first conference is to present and discuss the latest research that contributes to the sharing of new theoretical, methodological and empirical knowledge and a better understanding in the area of education curriculum, learning method and media, assessment as well as the issue of Science, Social, Math, Language Literacy.

The detail of themes of this conference are as follows:

1. Climate Change, Energy and Enviromental Education
2. Literacy of Lesson Study and Learning Community
3. The Use of ICT Based Media In Teaching and Learning
4. Technological, Pedagogical, Content Knowledge for Teaching
5. Students Higher Order Thinking Skill
6. The Integration of Soft Skill in Learning and Teaching

7. Contextual Teaching and Learning, Students Centered Learning, Whole Brain Teaching, Hypno-Teaching
8. Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Approach
9. Local Wisdom Based Education
10. Science, Social, Math, Language Literacy
11. Assessment in Education
12. Showcase of Teaching and Learning
13. The Development of English School Curriculum for ASEAN + 8

The targeted participants are among research students, academics and researchers, scholars, scientist, teachers and practitioners all around the world of at least 250 papers are expected to be presented in this conference with 70:30 ratio on local and international presenter. On behalf of the Organising Committee, we motivate you to make this conference unforgettable and valuable event. We are looking forward to seeing you in our green campus of the University of Jember, East Java, Indonesia!

Prof. Dr. Suratno, M.Si.

Professor in Biology Education

Organising Committee

FKIP-University of Jember

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First Day, 13 May 2017

Time	Activities
07.30 – 08.30	Registration
08.30 – 09.00	Opening iconssed conference
09.00 – 12.00	Keynote Speakers
12.00 – 13.00	Break
13.00 – 15.00	Parallel Session 1
15.00 – 15.30	Break
15.30 – 17.30	Parallel Session 2

Second Day, 14 May 2017

Time	Activities
08.30 – 15.00	Field Trip: Payangan Love Beach (Obstional)

198.	STUDENT CENTERED LEARNING: IMPROVING STUDENTS' PARTICIPATION IN THE LEARNING PROCESS TROUGH PROBLEM SOLVING METHOD Pretty Eristia Arinda	Education Research	121	R 10
199.	The Use of World Wide Web for Teaching and Learning Legal English Supardi	Education Research	121	R 10
200.	THE TEACHER'S COMPETENCY TEST IN ASWERING EDUCATION QUALITY IN INDONESIA Jarkawi, Laelatul Anisah, Eka Sri Handayani Akhmad Rizhki Ridahani	Education Research	122	R 10
201.	Visual Literacy in Teaching History : A Critical Thinking Skills Students Rizqa Ayu Ega Winahyu, S.Pd	Education Research	122	R 11
202.	THE TRANSFORMATION OF OBJECT REPRESENTATIONS OF VISUAL STUDENT ON GEOMETRY PROBLEM SOLVING Feny Rita Fiantika	Education Research	123	R 11
203.	Development and Impact of the Implementation of an Integrated Scientific Moral-Values Instructional Model on Students' Moral-Character Instilling Badeni and Sri Saparahayuningsih	Education Research	123	R 11
204.	INTEGRATED DEVELOPMENT OF LEARNING MODEL SOFT SKILLS AND HARD SKILL COMPETENCE IN IMPROVING CITIZENS IN INSTITUTIONS LEARNING COURSE BEAUTY. Wiwin Herwina	Education Research	124	R 11
205.	STUDENTS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS TERRORIST NETWORKS IN THE NEWS ON TELEVISION	Education Research	124	R 11

important source for example, documents, archives, and fibers. So that the learner to access difficult. But now that the main problem is that when all easily accessible. Students must be good at processing information and of course bring up the students' critical thinking skills

Keywords: Literacy, Visual Lietasi, Teaching History, Critical Thinking Skills

THE TRANSFORMATION OF OBJECT REPRESENTATIONS OF VISUAL
STUDENT ON GEOMETRY PROBLEM SOLVING

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ABSTRACT

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*Development and Impact of the Implementation of an Integrated Scientific Moral-Values
Instructional Model on Students' Moral-Character Instilling*

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is (a) to develop an integrated moral-values instructional model for social studies insructional and, (2) to know the impact of the implementation of the model on the instilling of the moral-character of junior scondary school students (JS3). The research was conducted in the form of test-retest experiment. The results of this reserach showed that the implementation of the integrated scientific moral-values istructional model on instructional process of social studies is able to increase more than 26 % of the instilling the moral-characters compared to the implenentation scientific approach contained in the content of social studies to the student intact.

Keywords: development, implementation, moral-character, and* integrated scientific instructional model

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by Feny Rita Fiantika

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According Piaget stage of cognitive development of concrete operations aged (7 years-11 years). The 5th grade students are at the age of 11 years which is a critical phase in the development of cognitive concrete operations and before concrete operations stage with the consideration that the researcher designing the task of geometry problems based on these needs. The subjects in this study were 5th graders learning visual learning style because this study refers to the field of geometry that closely study with the visualization of an object.

THE TRANSFORMATION OF OBJECT REPRESENTATIONS

Spatial thinking is essential to both human adaptation and modern living mental, because spatial thinking is mental process with amalgam of three element concepts of space, tool of representation and process of reasoning (NRC, 2006). According to Liben (2014) that spatial thinking is thinking that finds meaning in the shape, size, orientation, location, direction or trajectory of objects, process or phenomena or the relative positions in space of multiple objects, process or phenomena and which uses the properties of space as a vehicle for structuring problem, for finding answers, and for expressing solutions. It means spatial thinking needs object to represent it. According to Rumelhart (1980) that in analyzing any kind of thought, it is useful to distinguish representation from transformation. Intrinsically, transformation of object representations becomes tool to describe representation. We need representation to communicate our idea to other people and transformation becomes important to help representation create. Transformation needs object to operate and representation needs transformation to create, so they are both depend on vise-versa.

Zacks et al. (2000) there are two classes of mental transformation seem particularly important to human cognition: object-based spatial representations and egocentric perspective transformation. Object-based transformations are imagined rotation or translations of objects relative to reference frame of environment. Egocentric perspective transformations are imagined rotations and transformation of one's point-of-view relative to that reference frame. They both are imagined rotations or translation of mental process with different aspect. Transformation of object representation, encoding operations establish mental representation of the spatial of the spatial word by mentally rotating object, mentally extrapolating, mentally extending. According to the dominant theory of mental imagery, the mental operations that we perform on actual and mental representations are internalizations of physical changes that we perceive as we interact in the world (Finkle and Shepard, 1986). Spatial judgments following such transformations differ systematically, suggesting that though the problem are formally equivalent, they are performed using computationally different procedures (e.g Huttenlocher and Presson 1973; Presson 1982; Wraga et.al.2000). The object changes with different manners, and directions. In this paper calls as operation, because we work to combine two or more ideas becomes unique ideas by mathematic framework. Transformation of object representations are include changing perspective (reference frame), changing orientation include mental rotation, transforming shapes, changing size, moving wholes and reconfiguring parts, changing perspective, we need changing orientation to change perspective. By changing orientation we can imagine an object in any different view by rotations or translations and once of them is entail imagining a new point of view in an object or environment. We chose one view of orientation to change perspective by reference frame. We need to change reference frame when we are in different dimension or filed. So, changing perspective has closely connection to changing orientation. Transforming shape needs skill to transform object to different form, include reconfiguring parts, detecting embedded figures. To transform object we need skill to change orientation by rotations or translations and change perspective or reference frame.

The researcher established transformations of object representations indicator are:

To define the perspective (reference frame) in marking the plain cube model that has been given with a point, changing the orientation of the cube model when determining the point on the other side of the given cube model. The assigned task is a possible task to do, the researcher gave a plain cube model and the subject is asked to mark the cube with a point corresponding to the image of the cube webs on the given geometry problem.

METHODOLOGY

Task

Problem 1

Reyhan gets the homework to mark a plain cube model that his teacher has given him. Help Reyhan to mark the model of the plain cube with dots so that it matches the dots shown in the image of the cube webs below. Write down the steps - steps you think

The Issue 1 above herein after referred to as Task of Geometric Paper 1 Two Dimensions to Three Dimensions (TMG 1-DT).

Problem 1A

Reyhan gets homework to mark a plain cube model that his teacher has given him. Help Reyhan to mark the model of the plain cube with dots so that it matches the dots shown in the image of the cube webs below. Write down the steps - steps you think

The above mentioned problem 1A is used for triangulation purposes. Issue 1A is hereinafter referred to as Task Problem Geometry 1A Two Dimensions to Three Dimensions (TMG 1A-DT).

Participants

There is 1 student visual learning style in elementary school in the 5th grades ages 11 years old. He is students with the average mathematical abilities category.

Procedures

There are 30 students in elementary school in the 5th grade, the researcher gave them mathematic test in a ranking by 3 categorization of mathematic ability test are high, middle and low. The second, the researcher gave them learning style test and categorizing their result by visual, auditor and kinesthetic. The subject is 1 student visual learning style in elementary school of 5th grade ages 11 years old. He is the subject with the average mathematical abilities category. The Researcher gave geometric problem solving 1 and geometric problem solving 1A one week after geometric problem solving 1. There are 2 tasks of geometric problem solving with similar content, the second test for data triangulation and get the valid data. The research explores data deeply by interview that takes in interview every subject complete doing his step.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

RESULTS

The process of visual representation of objects visual students in solving geometry problems are:

Choose a pole as a reference point of view; this is apparent when using the pole for reference to determine the opponent and the node on the next side. The process of choosing a pole involves the process of reasoning; it is seen when choosing a pole accompanied by consideration or reason of particular selection.

Choose the pole as start point a way of view, showed when he used the pole for starting finding "the opponent" and dots in next side of cube. Choosing process of pole loaded reasoning process because choosing process by consideration and reasoning.

In transforming the form, it is seen when the subject imagines in changing the shape of the cube webs into a shadow cube in his mind. This process of transforming involves the process of reasoning that is when manipulating the form by analogizing with robot transformers. In doing object transform, showed when he imagined change cube nets become a cube in his mental activities. He used manipulation object by analogic with imagine robotic transform. It showed reasoning process.

In using the frame of view / perspective to mark the side of the cube, this is seen when using the pole and the opponent that has been selected as a reference for rolling or rotating the cube to mark the next side of the cube. The reasoning process appears when considering a pole until it is decided on choosing a particular pole then its opponent based on the chosen pole and considering selecting the direction of movement until a certain direction of motion is taken by considering the technique of rolling or rotating until the appropriate technique is obtained. He used perspectives (Frame reference) for marking side of cube. Showed when he used "the pole" and "the opponent" as start point to rotate of translation cube when he marks the other side of cube. He takes consideration to choose "the pole".

In using dimensional transformation that is changing the perspective / perspective from 2 Dimensions to 3 Dimensions, looks at the tendency in using mental activity that is to imagine the change of shape from the webs into a shadow cube. The reasoning process appears when analogizing the movement of cube webs that turn into shadow cubes with robotic transformers transformed into cars in their minds.

In changing the orientation of changing the angle of view from one side of the cube to the other side, this is seen in the completion step is to always determine the different poles and opponents in marking each side of a cube, determine the direction of movement to change the position of the cube side of the shadow and then mark Cube model with dots. The process of determining the pole, the opponent, and the direction of the shadow cube movement is to decide where the pole, the opponent and the direction of the shadow cube movement are evidence of the involvement of the reasoning process in the transformation of object representations.

In changing the orientation of the object by rolling or rotating the cube, it is visible when marking the cube on the next side and affixing the dot on the side of the cube, the subject always stay in positions of the side to be marked at the top position. The reasoning process is seen when considering direction selection, motion techniques used to decide which direction is chosen with certain motion techniques.

DISCUSSION

The reasoning plays an important role in the formation of object representation. There is manipulation of forms involving analogical thinking, a change of way / orientation by using the terms "left, right, front, back, up and down, pole, opponent" that involving representation transformation operations Object "overthrow" and "rotate" object. In changing the viewing framework from 2 Dimensions to 3 Dimensions involves an orientation by using the translation and rotation transformation operation in mind. The subjects with age at critical period of concrete operations show start using abstract mindset but still use concrete operation stage.

CONCLUSION

Transformation of Object Representations relation elements shows in figure 1 bellow.

Figure 1 Transformation of Object Representations Relation elements.

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